

MEDICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF BALL AND BEAM FIXATION SYSTEMS

Mehmani Ilham Gasanaga,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medical assistant

Mehmani Vusala Rasim,

Azerbaijan Medical University, assistant

Aliyev Mammad Suad Afrail

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine,

Department of Terapeutik Dentistry, Assistant,

Department of Orthopedic Dentistry,

Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract

We have studied the effect of mechanical load and friction on the wear of the male and matrix of ball and beam fixation systems during their mechanical separation. A high level of fixation of cover removable dentures was revealed for 2 years, further maintenance of which can be ensured by replacing matrices. The analysis shows that the beam system significantly outperforms the ball system, due to the minimum loss of linear dimensions and does not require the restoration of the actual patric element.

Keywords: integumentary prosthesis, ball and bar fixation systems.

The functional ability of dentures directly depends on their content on the prosthetic bed, and that is why a reasonable, rational and prognostically justified approach to prosthetics is decisive, especially with preserved single teeth or roots that are capable, albeit to a lesser extent, of perceiving a masticatory load. A common tactic in this situation is the manufacture of partial plate dentures with a clasp fixation system, which in the process of using the prosthesis leads to an overload of the exhausted and already partially morphofunctionally damaged periodontium of abutment teeth. After all, with an "increased" crown height due to the loss of part of the bone support of the root, the force of horizontally directed loads on the abutment tooth increases [1,2,3].

To reduce the magnitude of the load, it is advisable to reduce it closer to the level of the gums and use ball fixators (root or extra-root) as repotential elements or a practical doctor who puts a beam fixation system before choosing a fixation system based on many components: the condition of the supporting teeth, the condition of the periodontium, interalveolar height, the position of the teeth relative to the alveolar process, bite, the patient's attitude to oral hygiene and, finally, the doctor's experience. There is another important criterion that should be taken into account - the predicted service life of the manufactured prosthesis, which depends on the fixation elements, in particular, the ability to maintain the initial shape and size when operating in the aggressive environment of the oral cavity [4,5].

The purpose of the study is a comparative assessment of the effect of mechanical loading and wear friction on the change in the forces of separation of the male from the matrix of ball and beam fixation systems during their mechanical separation.

Materials and research methods

For the study, mechanical means of fixation were used, namely: a male and a reinforced matrix of the VSPGS beam connection and the ball joint - VKS-OTs $\varnothing 1.7$ mm. The male parts of both types of connection

were cast from an especially hard alloy. To study the change in the retention property of the matrix depending on the number of cycles of connection - separation of the matrix from the male, a device was used that makes it possible to measure the force by which the male and matrix are separated by increasing the weight of the sample by 0.1N. The base number of cycles "shooting - overlay" was 10000 cycles, the measurement was carried out after every 200 cycles. This measurement interval corresponds to a period of use of the prosthesis of 2 months [6]. In parallel with measuring the separation force of the friction pair, the diameter of the working (spherical) surface of males, both ball and beam, was measured. Before testing, instrumentally, with an accuracy of ± 0.01 mm, the diameter of the spherical surface of a ball metal male was measured at eight diametrically opposite points, and for a beam system, the diameter of the cylindrical part of the beam was measured at several places selected along the length of the generatrix.

The process of friction in a pair of male-matrix of any of these systems leads to abrasion of both surfaces. The males are characterized by the roughness of the surfaces of the working part, due to the height of the sharp irregularities of the metal surface, and the protrusions of the polymer on the surface of the matrix are somewhat less smooth. During their interaction, the matrix is erased, which is accompanied by the detachment of particles of its surface by the microroughness of the male, which are subsequently carried out outside the contact surface. The course and intensity of the process depends on the physical and chemical properties of materials, loading conditions, microgeometric characteristics of friction surfaces, etc. In addition, taking into account the multifactorial nature of the friction process, the wear process is affected by a combination of external conditions arising on the friction surface: sliding speed, change in the value of the latter, load of the friction pair, the nature of the action of the loading

force, the temperature factor, the configuration of friction surfaces that affects the distribution of contact pressures, and many other factors that determined the experimentally obtained quantitative indicators of wear [7].

Research results

The obtained results of the experiment showed that for the VKS-OTs ball male $\varnothing 1.7$ mm with a matrix of increased rigidity, wear began from about 350 cycles and continued until reaching 5000 cycles. For the VSP-GS male with a matrix of increased rigidity, wear began after about 500-600 cycles, which lasted until the index of 5000 cycles was reached. Further, the diameters of both types of males stabilized and remained unchanged until the index of 10,000 cycles was reached. A characteristic feature of the wear of the male of the ball attachment was that it occurred evenly until the diameter of 1.64 mm was reached in 5000 cycles, after which it remained unchanged. The wear of the beam male before reaching 5000 cycles was a meager value - 0.001 mm.

The study of the dynamics of the degree of retention of the fixation elements of integumentary prostheses with different methods of fixation made it possible to trace the nature of the changes depending on the number of "shooting-application" movements, i.e. on the period of use of the prosthesis (2880 prosthesis overlays = 2 years of use).

Analysis of numerical values showed that the initial retention force of integumentary prostheses with a ball fixation system was the largest and amounted to 24.4 ± 7.7 N. In prostheses with a bar fixation system, this value was less and averaged 21.4 ± 1 N.

It was found that the retention force in both groups did not differ significantly and equaled, on average, 23.1 N.

After 360 cycles (approximately 3 months of clinical use), a large retentive force was observed in prostheses with a bar fixation system and equaled, on average, 18.1 ± 2.4 N. In prostheses with a ball

fixation system, the retention force was 15.0 ± 3.9 N. After 720 cycles (≈ 6 months of clinical use), the retention force of 17.2 ± 3.0 N was higher for the bar fixation system, and for the ball system, this value became smaller and was 11.7 ± 2.0 N, statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$), while for prostheses with a button system it was 9.1 ± 1.8 N, the differences in these cases are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

After 1440, 1800 and 2160 cycles, the retention force in prostheses with a bar fixation system was further maintained at higher rates and amounted to 13.8 ± 3.1 N, 11.9 ± 4.3 N, 8.6 ± 2.1 N, respectively, in prostheses with ball fixation system - 7.4 ± 1.4 N, 6.9 ± 1.9 N, 6.1 ± 2.0 N, respectively. The differences are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). After 2520 shots, equivalent to 1 year and 9 months of using the prosthesis, the retention force of 7.6 ± 2.1 N was also greater in prostheses with a bar fixation system, and in prostheses with a

ball system, this value was 5.5 ± 1.9 N, the differences are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). For prostheses with ball and bar fixation systems, the retention force after 2880 exposures (≈ 2 years of using the prosthesis) was 4.9 ± 1.4 N and 6.9 ± 2.7 N, respectively, the differences are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

According to the results of experimental retention studies of the properties, against the background of a gradual decrease in the retention force with two types of fixation systems, a high level of fixation of overdentures for 2 years can be traced, further maintenance of which can be ensured by replacing matrices. At the same time, the analysis of the loss of linear dimensions indicates that the beam system significantly outperforms the ball system in this indicator, given the minimum loss of linear dimensions, and does not require restoration of the patristic element itself. Regardless of the type of mechanical fastening, the duration of the prosthesis service is closely related to the need for orthopedic compensation of temporary alveolar process atrophy.

References

1. Kljuchkovskaja N.R. Sposob uluchshenija fiksacii s#emnyh konstrukcij protezov/Kljuchkovskaja N.R. // Materialy mezhdunarodn. nauch. – upr. konf. «Sovremennye napravlenija razvitija stomatologicheskoi nauki i praktiki», 3-4 marta 2011 g. – Poltava, 2011. – S. 31-32.
2. Gromov O. V. Balochnoe kreplenie firmy "bredent": raznoobrazie i mnogofunkcional'nost' / Gromov O. V. // Zubnoe protezirovanie. – 2006. – №2. – S. 12-19.
3. Davis D. M. Kreplenie s#emnyh protezov / Davis D. M. // Stomatolog. – 2006. – №6. – S. 39-40.
4. Shherba P. V. Pokazaniya k ispol'zovaniju edinichnyh zubov i kornej kak fiksirujushih jelementov s#emnyh pokrovnyh protezov / P.V. Shherba, N. R. Kljuchkovskaja // Ukrainskij stomatologicheskij al'manah. – 2006. – №1. – S. 82-84.
5. Kalivradzhijan Je. S. Funkcional'noe sostojanie opornyh tkanej proteznogo lozha pod bazisami s#emnyh konstrukcij zubnyh. protezov/Je. S. Kalivradzhijan, I. P. Ryzhova// Sovremennaja ortopedicheskaja stomatologija – 2005. – №3. – S. 63-64.
6. Dzhaforova A.R. Abbasova E.M. Effektivnost' ozonoterapii pri lechenii periimplantitov. Suchasna stomatologiya 3 (111) 2022
7. Ispol'zovanie balochnykh konstruksii s oporoi na implantaty pri izgotovlenii polnykh s'emnykh protezov.(Annali D;Italia №33 2022 st 67 Itali) Panakhov N.,Safarov M.,Kerimova G.Ashrafvov D.S <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6907673>